

PRIORITY DIRECTIONS OF EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE SCIENCE OF "LIFE ACTIVITY SAFETY"

¹Narziev Shovkiddin Murtozaevich, ²Oxunov Ravshan Zafarovich

¹T.e. Professor of Tashkent State Technical University

²T.e. associate professor of the National University of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8054478>

Abstract. *Throughout its history, mankind has been fighting against natural phenomena and protecting itself from them. When we pay attention to the material and spiritual heritage left by our ancestors, we see how deeply the harmony between nature and man has left a mark on it. Today, humanity realizes that it is facing a big problem whether it knows it or not. Man saw this problem in the fact that the consequences of his own discoveries become dangerous factors for him. At this time, man tried to dominate nature. As a result, borderless dangers began to cause problems that need to be solved not only for one or a few nations, but also on a global scale.*

Keywords: *natural phenomena, protecting, discoveries, consequences.*

Introduction. It is known that a person has always put ensuring his safety as one of the primary tasks in any type of activity. Therefore, ensuring safety in life and in various fields of activity has been and continues to be one of the most important aspects of scientific and practical interests of mankind from the distant past to the present day. Because security problems are an important issue related to human health and life, as well as the level of development of society. As a result of the intensive development of production, the formation of the technosphere created requirements for the acquisition of special knowledge to solve security problems in it [1].

Therefore, protection against various risks, including harmful factors of the production environment, is very important. The current state and prospects of labor protection, as well as the issues of the impact of the results of socio-economic reforms in our republic and territorial security problems on the development trend of science, ensuring safety in the fields of human activity, and the creation of comfortable working environment conditions, theoretically and practically prepare specialists. It covers the issues of teaching to act and protect, as well as the impact on the environment [2].

Throughout its history, mankind has been fighting against natural phenomena and protecting itself from them. When we pay attention to the material and spiritual heritage left by our ancestors, we see how deeply the harmony between nature and man has left a mark on it. Today, humanity realizes that it is facing a big problem whether it knows it or not. Man saw this problem in the fact that the consequences of his own discoveries become dangerous factors for him. At this time, man tried to dominate nature [3]. As a result, borderless dangers began to cause problems that need to be solved not only for one or a few nations, but also on a global scale.

In the years of independence, especially after the formation of the Ministry of Emergencies and the state system of prevention and action in emergency situations in Uzbekistan, comprehensive cooperation with other countries developed rapidly. Uzbekistan was recognized by the World Health Organization as a country with a stable epidemiological situation [2,3].

The teaching of the academic subject "Safety of Life Activities" enables the student to learn about various emergency situations that occur in the world, to identify their dangers in advance, to learn the methods of protection in case of occurrence, to organize the right actions and to help people in need of help around them. It is aimed at providing, taking them out of dangerous areas, providing first aid, as well as being able to protect material assets from such dangers [4].

The main focus in teaching this subject is to teach the basics of personal and public safety, to be able to see and evaluate dangerous situations, and to teach the actions to be taken in emergency situations at home, on the street, in public transport, during the teaching of science, the main goal was to create stereotypes of self-protection and public protection in the mind of each student. Accordingly:

- imparting knowledge on teaching learners to protect their life and health during work;
- to teach how to eliminate damages in case of accidents;
- to teach ways of self-help and mutual aid in case of injuries caused by accidents;
- issues of learning to anticipate, assess and find ways to protect against dangerous situations are the essence of science.

When reviewing the scientific and pedagogical literature, we can see that in the process of conducting experimental work on a specific problem, the main attention should be paid to the practical aspects of the researched problem [5].

Table 1

**Theory of the pedagogical foundations of organizational skills
awareness of knowledge and skills**

№	Awareness of the theoretical knowledge and skills of pedagogical foundations of organizational skills	Total number of students			
		Experimental group n1=58		Experimental group n1=58	
		Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1	Love for work, interest in working with children.	15	43	29	31
2	Initiative, something in children	18	40	17	43
3	ability to arouse enthusiasm and interest in work	14	44	23	37
4	The ability to understand children, to see their good and bad qualities, to perceive how they perceive the lesson material, to objectively assess their knowledge and abilities, to be a practicing psychologist.	20	38	21	39
5	Having a high general culture, versatile knowledge, significant pedagogical knowledge and skills.	21	37	24	36
6	Ability, knowledge and interest in one's subject, and desire to expand one's knowledge of one's subject.	19	39	25	35

7	Strength, activity, striving for the goal, volitional qualities.	24	34	20	40
8	Positive attitude to work.	13	45	23	37
9	Ability to share knowledge, feelings, beliefs, thoughts with others.	8	50	12	48
10	Organizational ability.	14	44	15	45
11	Ability to manage a team of children.	18	40	11	49
12	A sense of responsibility, humility, a constant desire to improve one's skills, the ability to notice and correct one's own shortcomings.	16	42	12	48

Pedagogical process is a process that illuminates the content of practical activity that takes place between the teacher (teacher-pedagogue) and the learner (pupil-students) and exhibits didactic features. Theoretical pedagogical ideas are decided on the basis of studying, analyzing and summarizing the essence of the educational and educational process in direct practice. Therefore, in the process of pedagogical research, the organization of experimental tests appears as the main core of this process [5]. Based on the above-mentioned ideas, at the beginning of the experiment-testing organized for the formation of organizational skills in students, the levels of formation of students are reflected in the table below (Table 1).

The figures in the table above show that the level of knowledge acquired by the students in the pedagogical system of forming organizational skills in the course of work in the auditorium and outside the auditorium is low.

As a result of practical testing of the specially prepared methodology for pedagogical experiments, students' organizational skills have significantly changed. This change is reflected in the following table [5,6].

In order to determine the level of complete learning of the content of organizational skills by students during classroom and non-auditory classes, we developed a questionnaire that embodies the essence of this idea in detail (see Table 2).

When we performed a mathematical statistical analysis of the experimental tests, we obtained the following results: This questionnaire was brought to the attention of students at the beginning and at the end of the experimental tests [6]. At the beginning and end of the experimental work, the indicators recorded by the students of the experimental and control groups were compared and processed using the mathematical and statistical method. This situation confirmed the effectiveness of the methodology developed by us and tested in practice during the experimental work.

In higher educational institutions with pedagogical potential, a training was organized on the formation of organizational concepts in the mathematical-statistical analysis of the pedagogical aspects of using interactive methods in the formation of organizational skills among students. Their results were compared with the current control work conducted in this group. The evaluation was carried out according to the N-hypothesis 84, that is, if the average grades of the control works differ less than the high confidence level, then the materials on the formation of organizational sentences are considered to be mastered by students in the same way [7].

In order to show the formation of concepts related to organization in the assessment of students' knowledge, we calculated the results of control work conducted in experimental and control groups. This is represented in Table 2 [7,8].

Table 2

The result of testing the methodology specially prepared for pedagogical experiments in practice

№	Awareness of the theoretical knowledge and skills of the pedagogical foundations of organizational skills	Total number of students			
		Experimental group n1=58		Control group n2=60	
		Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1	Love for work, interest in working with children.	46	12	24	234
2	Initiative, the ability to arouse enthusiasm and interest in something in children.	50	8	13	47
3	The ability to understand children, to see their good and bad qualities, to feel how they perceive the lesson material, to objectively evaluate their knowledge and abilities, to be a practicing psychologist.	47	11	14	46
4	Having a high general culture, versatile knowledge, significant pedagogical knowledge and skills.	39	19	25	35
5	Ability, knowledge and interest in one's subject, and desire to expand one's knowledge of one's subject.	55	3	24	36
6	Strength, activity, striving for the goal, volitional qualities.	43	15	27	43
7	Positive attitude to work.	42	16	28	32
8	Knowledge, feelings,	52	6	27	33
9	ability to share beliefs and thoughts with others.	48	10	24	36
10	Organizational ability	51	7	18	42

One of the main principles in the implementation of personnel training is the retraining of teachers and trainers in order to reform the educational system in terms of structure and content, harmonizing the activities of educational institutions for training highly qualified, competitive specialists, advanced introduction of pedagogical technologies and pedagogical innovations into the educational process. But advanced pedagogical technologies and innovations do not enter the education system by themselves [8]. This process depends on the activity of the teacher and his motivation. One step forward in education cannot be made without changing the activity of the teacher, without increasing his responsibility and activity. Academician A.N. Leontev "The first condition for understanding the world is activity, and the second condition is education."

In the process of activity, people's abilities, knowledge and skills are formed, therefore, activity is a social phenomenon and is the main condition of life struggle," he says [9]. Today, as a result of the emergence of a new scientific direction in the field of pedagogy - pedagogical innovation and the idea of renewing the educational process, a new direction in the pedagogical

activity of the teacher, the concept of "innovative activity of the teacher" has appeared. Analyzing the concept of "innovative activity", G.A. Mkritichyan's opinion about it is worthy of attention: - "3 main forms of pedagogical experiment-test activity can be distinguished: private experience, experiment-test work, innovative activity of the teacher.

The more innovations in pedagogical activity, the better the teacher understands the private experiment" [10]. Innovative activity refers to the creative approach of a pedagogue to mastering existing forms and tools for improving his profession.

It should also be recognized that the scientific ideas and classifications that are stable and acceptable to everyone about innovations in education and innovative pedagogical activity have not been fully formed until now. One of the main reasons for this situation is the difficult-to-overcome discontinuity between education-oriented scientific knowledge systems. An even bigger reason is the disconnection between educational knowledge and practical pedagogical activity.

As a subject and organizer of innovative activity, the teacher participates in the creation, application and popularization of innovation. He should be able to analyze the content and essence of changes in scientific knowledge and traditions. The concept of innovative activity is closely related to such concepts as innovation, innovative process. Therefore, it is impossible to understand the content of innovative activity without understanding the content of these concepts. Innovation is an important part of practice and theory, a system of action of social subjects aimed at improving the qualities of a socio-cultural object [11].

There are different approaches and opinions regarding the creation of the essence of this idea theory, and there is no unified opinion in science about its essence. Innovations are relevant, important, new approaches formed in one system. They are born on the basis of initiatives and innovations, are promising for the development of educational content, and also have a positive effect on the development of the education system as a whole. Innovation is the use of technology, forms and methods in a certain field of activity or production, a new approach to solving a problem or a new technological process, which is known to lead to greater success than before.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2017 йил 20 апрелдаги “Олий таълим тизимини янада ривожлантириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги ПҚ–2909-сонли Қарори
2. Нарзиев Ш. М. Рахимова Азиза Хусан Кизи Применение и анализ педагогических методов в учебном процессе. – 2021.
3. “Та’лим то’ғ’рисида”ги О’zbekiston Respublikasi Qonuni. 2020 yil 23 sentyabr, О’RQ-637-son. <https://lex.uz/docs/5013007>
4. Mark, P. Friend James Fundamentals of Occupational Safety and Health. Bernan Press. Германия, 2014.
5. Ишмухамедов Р., Мирсалиева М “Ўқув жараёнида инновацион таълим технологиялари” Тошкент 2014 й.
6. “Student Response Systems.” Teaching at Mizzou: A Guide for New Faculty, Graduate Instructors and Teaching Assistants website. Retrieved 4 March 2005 from: <http://teachandlearn.missouri.edu/guide/chapters/activelearning.htm>.
7. E.I.Ibragimov, S.Gazinazarova, O.R.Yuldashev. Mehnat muhofazasi maxsus kursi. Amaliy mashg’ulotlar. O’quv qo’llanma.-T.: TIMI – 2014.

8. Murtozvevich, N. S., Ziyoxiddinovich, A. A., & oglu, K. K. H. (2022). Methodology of labor process organization. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(6), 152-157. Retrieved from <https://www.cajotas.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJOTAS/article/view/573>
9. Qudratov A. va b. "Mehnat muhofazasi". Ma'ruza kursi. -T.: "Aloqachi" 2005.-355 b.
- A. Khokimoyatov, Sh. Narziev Analysis of methods for determining dangerous and harmful factors in the labor process // SAI. 2023. №A5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/analysis-of-methods-for-determining-dangerous-and-harmful-factors-in-the-labor-process> (дата обращения: 17.06.2023).
10. Аҳоли ва худудларни фавқулодда вазиятлардан муҳофаза қилишнинг ҳуқуқий асослари (меъёрий-ҳуқуқий ҳужжатлар тўплами). I-том. Адолат. –Т.: 2007 й. -328 б.
11. Нарзиев Шовкиддин Муртозаевич, Ботиров Акбар Бахриддинович Безопасность деятельности человека методы изучения и анализа рисков в трудовом процессе // ТЕСНика. 2021. №1-2 (5-6). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bezopasnost-deyatelnosti-cheloveka-metody-izucheniya-i-analiza-riskov-v-trudovom-protssesse> (дата обращения: 17.06.2023).